

CST4ALL

Support to the Activities of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technology Area of the SET Plan

CST4ALL Final project closing event

Date	9 September 2025
Time	09:00 – 16:30 CEST
Hybrid event	Meeting venue: L42 business center & workspaces (Rue de la Loi 42, B-1040 Brussels, Belgium) Remote participation via Microsoft Teams
Registration link	For in-person attendance For remote participation

Agenda

09:00	Welcome coffee
09:30	Opening address and CST4ALL project objectives Peter Heller – <i>German Aerospace Center (DLR)</i>
09:45	Message from the European Commission Marina Montero Carrero – <i>DG Research and Innovation, European Commission</i>
10:00	Message from the CST IWG Cristina Trueba – <i>Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies Implementation Working Group (CST IWG) Chair</i>
10:15	Presentation of project results – Session I <i>Progress on CST Implementation Plan targets</i> Ricardo Sánchez Moreno – <i>CIEMAT - Plataforma Solar de Almería</i> <i>Findings from R&I perspective</i> Peter Heller – <i>German Aerospace Center (DLR)</i> Q&A
11:30	Coffee break

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101075408.

11:45 Presentation of project results – Session II

Findings from industry perspective

Konstantinos Genikomsakis – *European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (ESTELA)*

SSH and gender aspects

Hande Eryilmaz – *ODTÜ-GÜNAM Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications*

Q&A

13:00 Lunch break

14:15 Roundtable discussion on EU cross-technology cooperation perspectives

Moderator:

Simona De Iuliis – *Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA)*

Participants:

Beatrice Coda – *DG Research and Innovation, European Commission*

Joachim Krueger – *President of ESTELA*

Thomas Garabetian – *SolarPower Europe / Secretariat of ETIP PV*

Greg Arrowsmith – *Secretary-General of EUREC / Secretariat of RHC-ETIP*

Leonie Kuhlmann – *European Geothermal Energy Council / Secretariat of ETIP-Geothermal*

16:15 Wrap-up and conclusions

Peter Heller – *German Aerospace Center (DLR)*

16:30 End of event

CST4ALL Coordinator

DLR Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt
German Aerospace Center

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum für Luft - und Raumfahrt e.V. (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ITALIAN NATIONAL AGENCY FOR NEW TECHNOLOGIES,
ENERGY AND SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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